

TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REFLEXIVE ABILITIES OF FUTURE TEACHERS IN THE UNIVERSITY

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Annotation: The article deals with the conditions of modernization of higher education, there is a need to use innovative methods and technologies in the process of preparing students for future professional activities. The introduction of state educational standards into the educational process of professional educational institutions based on a competent approach does not exclude the possibility of using reflexive technologies in the educational process at a university and the formation of reflexive abilities of future preschool teachers in this process.

Key words: Activity, modernization, reflection, process, development, specificity, spirituality, technology.

Reflection (from late Latin reflexio - turning back, reflection), a form of human theoretical activity aimed at comprehending one's own actions and their laws; the activity of self-knowledge, revealing the specifics of the spiritual world of man. The presence of reflection in a person allows a person to consciously plan, regulate and control his thinking; allows you to evaluate not only the truth of thoughts, but also their logical correctness; reflection allows you to find answers to problems that cannot be solved without its application.

A.A. Bizyaeva understands pedagogical reflection as a complex psychological phenomenon, manifested in the ability of a teacher to enter into an active research position in relation to his activity and to himself as its subject in order to critically analyze, comprehend and evaluate its effectiveness for personality development.

Reflexive-activity technologies of professional development are characterized by:
a reflexive approach to the organization of educational and cognitive activity of students, which involves the creation of a reflexive educational environment that contributes to the awareness of their own tasks in each specific educational situation;

meaningful reflective analysis of educational material in order to identify various invariants that allow students to independently plan and carry out educational and cognitive (educational and professional) activities;

the use of educational technologies focused on training goals: first personal, then professionally significant;

the use of didactic methods and techniques aimed at organizing students' self-government by their personal and professional development, at activating students' independence and creativity in finding ways and means to solve their personal and professionally significant problems;

introduction of organizational forms of educational and cognitive activity of students, activating such reflexive mechanisms of personal and professional self-development as reflexive control, reflexive assessment, reflexive analysis, etc. (N.G. Alekseev, O.S. Anisimov,

Yu.V. Gromyko, V. V. Davydov, S. D. Neverkovich, I. N. Semenov, A. A. Tyukov, G. P. Shchedrovitsky, etc.) [2].

Meanwhile, the results of scientific research show that future teachers of preschool educational institutions - university students do not have enough reflexive abilities, which is reflected in their insufficient practical preparation for educational activities in preschool educational institutions, the ability to use methods and means of reflection on pupils to solve the tasks.

The future educator of a preschool educational institution needs to have pedagogical attitudes that correspond to the personal and professional qualities that are necessary improve daily through self-education or with the help of formed reflective abilities. A reflective educator is a thinking, analyzing, investigating teacher. This, as D. Dewey said, is "an eternal student of his profession" with an indefatigable need for self-development and self-improvement.

The general ability to reflect is presented as a set of individual skills, in particular: the ability to control one's actions, including intellectual ones; the ability to see the unknown in the known, the unusual in the obvious, that is see contradiction; the ability to track the logic of the development of one's thought (judgment); the ability to take the positions of different "observers"; the ability to implement a dialectical approach to the analysis of the situation.

The mastery of the future teacher of the preschool educational institution by pedagogical reflection implies the formation of a kind of humanistic orientation in him, including the search for the meaning of his profession, the choice of a professional position.

The process of development of pedagogical reflection in a university is a multilevel, multidimensional process, a kind of technological and pedagogical system based on the technological and communicative interaction of all participants in educational activities, diagnostics of the results of the development process. All this helps students to comprehend their future practical activities, conduct constant introspection and analysis, form an adequate understanding and regulation of their pedagogical activities and the activities of students (pupils).

Changes are taking place in the personal self-development of students, suggesting the emergence of a stable orientation to "feedback", first of all, with oneself; skills are developed to predict possible own difficulties, to systematize their results, to model their learning activities, taking into account the accumulated (albeit small) reflective experience. As a result, students are more actively involved in work at seminars and practical classes, in the work of problem groups, scientific and practical conferences, competitions, etc.

The reflexive skills of future preschool teachers can be formed in the following ways:

- 1) through the inclusion of special methods of reflective learning in traditional pedagogical courses, for example, "Introduction to pedagogical activity", "General foundations of pedagogy", "Pedagogical technologies" and others.
- 2) through a module on the formation of reflexive skills of future educators, presented as an independent special practice, as a result of which students develop an interest in their future profession, a pedagogical orientation develops, i.e. pedagogical disciplines play the role of a

foundation on the basis of which future educators form professional skills and abilities in the study of special disciplines.

The multiple reflective methods or technologies that exist today and are used in the educational process can be divided into the following types:

Dialogue techniques. These may include techniques based on dialogue and involving the author's statement and its understanding. Such techniques are built on the basis of the first phase of complex communication, or discussion. Mandatory conditions for the emergence of a dialogue are listening to the author's statement, asking questions to clarify or understand what was said. Without understanding, there is no dialogue; an objection without understanding gives rise to a meaningless dispute in which new knowledge does not arise.

The dialogue technique is reflexive, since it reveals both personal reflection, associated with the individuality of a person and his volitional orientation, and intellectual, which allows thinking about someone else's thoughts, and activity, expressed in the choice of an act with a new norm. The dialogue technique can become a condition for creative activity, since creative exits from reflection occur as a result of a "wordless, hidden" dialogue of a person with himself.

Interactive Interactives implemented in various forms of games, in discussions and having the following features also act as reflective methods:

the content of the discussed material and tasks should be based on the existing life, professional and other experience of the audience;

the introductory lecture (introductory, introductory) should be problematic roaring;

the teacher should encourage the audience to try to represent the situation unambiguously, but multidimensionally, to offer not one and not unambiguous solution, but variable, flexible, etc.;

the teacher should organize the discussion taking into account the personal potential of the students: encourage independence in thinking and activity, welcome and even provoke the emergence of a different point of view, independence, responsibility, etc.;

interactive as a form (procedure) should be based on the reflection procedure (rationing, analysis, criticism) both in the discussion part and in the organization of group or individual reflection;

the composition of the interactive should include problematization (introductory lecture), the organization of individual and group reflection to solve the problems posed, discussions based on complex communication, individual reflection following the discussion.

From the point of view of the reflexive method, the most effective among interactive games are educational games built according to the type of organizational-activity and organizational-thinking games.

Formation of socio-professional competencies by the case study method. A common and effective technique for analyzing specific situations (from the English case - a case). It is built on the analysis of examples, on which students learn to avoid mistakes made by others in practical activities. For analysis, situations are proposed (by type of tasks), in which the initial conditions are given and it is required either to find a solution option or to make adjustments to the existing solution. This technique allows you to include such elements of reflection as analysis and normalization. The case solving technique teaches to draw general conclusions

from particular examples, forms the skill of practical use of general rules and techniques. Reflective discussion. A reflexive discussion consists in the fact that one group proposes a project or models a problem situation, the other offers alternative ways to optimize or resolve it, the third gives constructive additions for its development. During the lesson, the groups change roles, which allows them to “live” each role, reflect on the position of both authors and critics, enrich the content and gain experience in cultural interactions and reflection on various activities. Reflective discussion allows not only to form a database of various professional innovations, but also to ensure the process of their critical analysis.

Reflective video training. An effective form of reflective technique is a reflective video training. It greatly enhances the effectiveness of reflective processes for personal and professional growth. The effectiveness of reflective video training lies in the fact that it creates a holistic

reflexive-developing environment, which is based on personal and intellectual reflection. In addition, during the training, co-creation relationships are developed between the participants due to cooperative and individual reflection, which ensures an intensive process of self-development and self-realization. This contributes to the rethinking of one's own experience and the development of professional competence.

Reflective games. For reflexive games, which are based on the reflexive method, it is typical to familiarize participants with a democratic way of behavior, teaching psychotherapeutic relaxation of group tension, and stimulating deep associations. Games are designed to enhance the learning effect of training. Experts emphasize that the special didactic value of games is due to the fact that a person better learns the processes that occur in real life in professional activities. The effectiveness of the game depends on its dynamism and personal involvement of the participants, on the environment in which they need to analyze emerging situations and decisions. The obligatory presence of surprise, and in some cases, conflict, the informality of the situation, the dynamism of the change in the situation and its dependence on the decisions of the participants in the game also enhance the effectiveness of the game.

Reflective-innovative seminar. One of the most commonly used techniques is the reflective-innovative workshop. The main goal of the seminar is to develop the skills of the participants to organize their own activities and interactions in conditions of high uncertainty and inefficiency of the previously used tools and systems. During the seminars, the participants deal not only with problems, but also with new, unknown factors in the activity and situation. At the same time, they learn to work with uncertainty of a high order and analyze the foundations and mechanisms of their activities carried out in this uncertainty.

The use of reflective technologies in the educational process is of particular importance for future teachers, and in particular, for future preschool teachers. This is explained by the fact that the reflexive-personal orientation in the process of professional training of teachers affects the development of personality, self-awareness, self-realization and self-actualization, the disclosure of creative potential as necessary psychological prerequisites for the formation of the self-concept, as well as the types of competence that implement it, psychologically providing thinking, communication, understanding of management as components of the reflective professional culture of a modern teacher. Mastering the latter ensures the personal, professional, social and creative growth of the teacher.

The development of new approaches and models of professional training of future educators requires taking into account the current realities of the development of the higher education system associated with Russia's entry into the Bologna process, into the zone of a unified European higher education. The effective formation of the reflexive abilities of educators can become one of the conditions for the successful implementation of new educational tasks, namely, the provision of specialists with a high level of professional competence and competitiveness to the labor market.

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